

Structural, electrical and optical properties of Ba, Ni modified KNbO₃semiconducting ferro electric ceramics

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Abstract

Ferroelectric semiconducting ceramics with band gap (E_g) < 2 eV will be very useful for the photovoltaic and photocatalytic application. Unfortunately all the current ferroelectric oxides have wide band gaps (E_g > 2.7 eV for BiFeO₃, E_g > 3.5 eV for PZT) [1,2] and can utilize only about 8%–20% of the solar spectrum and efficiency is very small. Recently, Grinberg et al. [3,4] invented a complex ceramic solid solution of KNbO₃-BaNiNbO₃ (KN-BNNO) which is ferroelectric and has a band gap < 2 eV. However, the problems associated with the development of the KNbO₃-based materials lies on its complex densification behavior and alkali evaporation leading to poor density. There are no literatures available for the preparation of dense KN-BNNO ceramics and its electrical characterization. The present paper reports the effect of Ni doping and Ba, Ni co-substitution in KNbO₃ on phase evolution, electrical, optical properties and photocatalytic behavior. The temperature dependence dielectric permittivity of modified KNbO₃ ceramics indicates that the doping level significantly modifies the phase transition temperature. Impedance spectroscopy is used to understand the electrical conduction behavior with doping and temperature. UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy indicates that Ni-doped and Ba-Ni co-doped KNbO₃ have significant absorption in the visible range. Photocatalytic activity evaluation displays an enhanced visible light photocatalytic activity of Ba-Ni co-doped KNbO₃ in degrading rhodamine B in comparison with KNbO₃.

Keywords: KNbO₃; Doping; Electrical properties;

References

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